

CRISIS MANAGEMENT AND COPING WITH CRISES IN A PRECISE WAY. FUNCTIONS, TYPES, AND FUTURE OF CRISIS MANAGEMENT

Asiyat Kurbanova¹, Nargiza Akhrorova²

¹Student of “Silk Road” International University of Tourism and Cultural Heritage, ²senior lecturer of “Silk Road” International University of Tourism and Cultural Heritage

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***Annotatsiya.** Inqiroz XXI asrda tez-tez uchraydigan hodisa, shuning uchun har bir kompaniya inqiroz menejmenti, menejment turlari, funksiyalari va ushbu yo‘nalishning kelajagi haqida asosiy bilimlarga muhtoj. Tadqiqot menejment inqirozi sohasidagi boshqa muhim ishlar yordamida amalga oshirildi. Ushbu ishning maqsadi o‘rtacha statistik odamga inqiroz menejmenti jarayoni haqida asosiy bilimlarni berish, uning funksiyalari va strategiyalarini, shuningdek, uning turlarini tushuntirish va yaqin kelajakda inqiroz menejmentining rivojlanishi bo‘yicha ba‘zi bashoratlarni amalga oshirishdir.*

***Аннотация.** Кризис это частое явление в двадцать первом веке, поэтому каждая компания нуждается в базовых знаниях о менеджменте кризисов, типах менеджмента, функциях, и будущем этого направления. Исследование проведено при помощи других значимых работ в сфере кризис менеджмента. Цель этой работы предоставить среднестатистическому человеку базовые знания о процессе менеджмента кризисов, объяснить его функции и стратегии, а также его типы, и сделать некоторые прогнозы по развитию кризис менеджмента в ближайшем будущем.*

***Abstract.** Crisis is a frequent phenomenon in the first century; therefore, every company needs to be aware of crisis management, its types, functions, and the future of that process. This research is done with the help of other significant works in the sphere of crisis management. The aim of that work is to make the general population get to know more about the crisis management process, explain its functions and strategies as well as its types, and give some predictions for the development of crisis management in the near future.*

***Keywords:** crisis management, crisis management functions, crisis management types, term crisis management, managing crises, crisis management future trends.*

Introduction

Nowadays, most companies and organizations are facing tons of crises every day. The first question that comes to the minds of readers is what is crisis management itself. The answer was given by Tubalec and coauthors in 2025: “Crisis management is an essential component of an organization's strategic development in the face of growing threats and global economic instability”. Actually, crisis is considered to be usual and moreover, unescapable state for today’s unstable economy. “It is difficult to discuss the operational dynamics of any modern enterprise without considering the potential for crises” (Postolov, et al., 2025). However, there are some ways to predict and present crises in organizations. Even if it was not done beforehand, a crisis can still be coped in less harmful way by implementing crisis management methods, which will be discussed further. Furthermore, taking into account only the functions of crisis managers and neglecting digital trends would be mistaken. Therefore, artificial intelligence and other innovative

technologies should be considered in the article because they are opening new paths of dealing with problems of the present economy. While it may not be clear why companies face crises and how they can tackle these kinds of issues, this article gives some fundamentals about the phenomenon of crisis management itself, as well as reviews functions and fundamental types of crisis management and gives some predictions for the future trends. Although crisis management is making enormous steps to the world of digital technologies and AI, there are still basic tasks and terms that should be considered by specialists in the sphere.

Literature review

This article is citing a list of research works that are relevant to the theme or mention important information about crisis management. First of all is the Cambridge Business English Dictionary, which provides terms and their definitions in the business sphere and in particular the term “crisis management” for this work. Article “Crisis Management in the context of Digital Transformation”, written by Tubalec, Ivah, no and others, overview theme of digital technologies in today's business in general and crisis management in particular. In the article titled “Crisis Management: Key Aspects and Current Practices” authors, including Tubalec and Pisareva, are making the revision of main terms and aspects of crisis management, revealing some basic information. Moreover, that research work reveals main strategies used in crisis management today, as well as changes over time. While the article of Tubalec and others is structuring the main parts of crisis management, research published by Aroshvili and coauthors gives information about tactics that are relevant in the modern world economic situation. Furthermore, that article provides the reader with reasons for increased frequency of crises in today's economy.

Research work “Crisis Management in IT Companies: The Case of Skopje”, accomplished by Postolov Brothers, covers a list of topics, including crisis management as a process, effective crisis management strategies nowadays, the possibility of crisis in modern society and case study from Skopje. Work, named “Krizový manažment vo verejnej správe”, lists main functions of crisis management, which are the base of the process of managing crises.

The last research to be mentioned is “Evaluation of Modern Approaches to Crisis Management”, wrote by Brezina and coauthors, provides full description of modern ways to tackle the crisis in the company.

What is Crisis Management?

Firstly, people need to have a basic understanding of crisis management and what it refers, because the importance of crisis management in the modern world cannot be neglected. The present situation all over the world proves that crisis is normal and usual state for 21 century's economics. Some researchers have already discussed the phenomenon of permanent possibility of crisis, including Aroshvili with coauthors, who wrote that: “In the modern global world, organizations must deal with crises at almost every stage, despite their scale and the period of the past” (2025). Postolovs were also talking about the inevitability of crises and the necessity of special strategies: “In modern business environments, the inevitability of crises has become widely recognized, and organizations are increasingly focusing on developing crisis management strategies to address them when they arise” (2025). Consequently, every business requires high-quality crisis management. Although it is obvious that the situation needs to be tackled in the most fluent and precise way, some entrepreneurs still continue to neglect the importance of crisis management specialists, significantly suffering in harsh periods for companies. Mainly, this happens because of unawareness of people about crisis management itself and its functions. Beginning with the term “crisis management,” one of the most understandable and basic

definitions is provided by Cambridge Business English Dictionary, which says that crisis management is “the actions that are taken to deal with an emergency or difficult situation in an organized way” (2011). So, the crisis management department helps organizations to stay in the market and continue being competitive even in a difficult time when a given company lacks resources or workforce, cannot cope with weather issues, political problems or even natural disasters. Managers are skilled at tackling problems by avoiding crisis situations, as well as by applying the most suitable strategy in order to ease the consequences of crisis and boost future development of the company. Therefore, employing a qualified crisis manager for the company has a considerable advantage that’s why most of the world's well-known companies have already taken measures by employing specialists to coordinate successfully during crises.

Functions of Crisis Management

While the topic of the necessity of crisis management and the term itself have already been reviewed, it is crucial to understand the functions and strategies of successfully resolving difficulties in business. Crisis management is a complex process that takes into account a list of factors, or according to Postolov: “Crisis management is a multifaceted process that integrates knowledge and theories from various fields” (Postolov, et al., 2025). To make the process easier of undertake and more structured for specialists, researchers have listed some main functions of crisis management:

“The basic theoretical model of crisis management is the “Šimák - basic model” which consists of four crisis management processes - prevention, crisis planning, response, and recovery”(Brezina, et al., 2024). Thus, the first function is preventing crisis. “In modern business environments, the inevitability of crises has become widely recognized, and organizations are increasingly focusing on developing crisis management strategies to address them when they arise” (Postolov, et al., 2025). So preventing crisis is the ability of specialist to recognize the possibility of forthcoming crisis and take steps to prevent consequences in advance. But unfortunately, sometimes managers cannot predict and prevent crisis due to some issues, including lack of trapping and in that situation the second and the following are necessary. Planning is crucial in any process related to business, same in the crisis management process, that’s why it is second function. To plan the resolution of a crisis correctly, professional should now about the inner situation in the business, the state of all main competitors, the financial side, weaknesses of the company and many other facts. In order to be aware of all those things from the inside, a crisis manager mostly needs to be a full-time member of staff. Planning crisis in one of the most complicated functions that needs a lot of patience, dedication, and decision-making. It was mentioned about decision making in the research held by Brezina with coauthors: “Decision-making is an important function of crisis management, and we can refer to it as multi-criteria decision making, and its importance increases during the resolution of crisis phenomena”(Brezina, et al., 2024). Although planning is essential, it is important to imply the plan in real life correctly. So now it is time for the third function- response. Response function refers to correct and precise steps, taken to minimize negative affects of crisis. “For managers, effective crisis management requires identifying the root causes of crises and also implementing strategies that minimize their negative consequences” (Postolov, et al., 2025). Structures implemented by company (response) straightly influence the overall situation as well as possible disadvantages, caused by crisis. Coming to the forth function, which is recovery. Even with accurate work of manager companies rarely overcome crisis without damage for organization itself and its profit in particular. Therefore crisis manager should have clear plan how to recover the company after crisis abd afterwards grow in

income more and more. As mentioned in 2024, “Each of the shortlisted crisis management concepts and models has its own specific status, principles, and environment in which the individual phases of crisis management are applied”(Brezina, et al.). Consequently all the functions and strategies can not be implemented in one particular situation. Action taken by manager are depending on surround facts.

Types of crisis management

Now generally, main functions of crisis management are reviewed, however it is crucial to observe types of it and their main spheres and responsibilities. As it was mentioned by Postolovs in 2025 crisis management can have different forms and variations, but general classification according to Muller (p. 38) includes 2 types of management: active crisis management and passive crisis management. Active crisis management is mostly taking into account only the first function of crisis management - preventing crisis. “Active crisis management refers to proactive measures taken to identify and mitigate potential crises before they occur” (Postolov, et al., 2025). The measures and steps used to predict and prevent crisis beforehand are called active crisis management. “In contrast, reactive crisis management involves responding to crises after they have occurred” (Postolov, et al., 2025). Passive crisis management strategies are used when crisis have already occurred and positions held by company started lowering. At that proper moment manager starts to response and take actions in reactive way. Although it can seem that active crisis management is more important to be able to apply by manager in order to escape negative consequences, however sometimes prevent crisis is impossible and manager should be skilled enough to use passive way of crisis management.

Future trends in crisis management

Nowadays, every sphere is overcoming global changes connected with innovative technologies of the new year, and crisis management is not an exception. More and more professional tasks are becoming less complex and time-consuming through the application of digital technologies and AI. The question is: “Is the massive use of technologies in every sphere affecting crisis management as well, and what consequences should be expected?” The answer to the first question is “yes, definitely it will affect in the future, moreover, digital development has already affected crisis management today”. managing crises is the complex process of planning, considering possibilities of positive and negative aspects, and finding out the risks of every variety of choice. The human brain is not able to do those tasks properly, while artificial intelligence is capable of doing that with significant accuracy. It is one of the main reasons of usage od digital technologies in management and in crisis management in particular. As mentioned in 2025, “The introduction of digital technologies, strategic flexibility, and the creation of a corporate culture that values adaptation are among the key elements and modern practices that are being taken into account” (Tubalec, et al., 2025). So nowadays business practices exist in coordination with modern technologies, which increases time management as well as economic advantage. Innovative technologies are reflecting the future of any sphere. “The integration of technologies such as cloud computing, big data analysis, artificial intelligence and process automation opens up new opportunities to increase efficiency, reduce costs and increase business sustainability” (Tubalec, et al., 2024).

Thus, technologies are opening new paths for companies in crisis management by reducing the number of employees (decreased financial waste), increasing variability of efficient actions according crisis, and high rate of stability after crisis due to estimated risks. While the list of advantages of implementing digital technologies in crisis management sphere is notable, there is

a number of drawbacks that should be considered as well. First of all if the company uses AI for multiple functions, it decreases its staff. For the company it is profitable, fewer wages- more money, but unfortunately, it can lead to increased rates of unemployment among the population. Secondly, as many researchers affirm, with the development of digital technologies the frequency of crises can increase significantly. It was mentioned by Brezina with coauthors in 2024: “In the course of time, with the development of society and technical and technological innovations of various kinds, the frequency of crisis phenomena has increased”. Therefore, although integration of digital technologies in crisis management is inescapable in the future, people should take into consideration some disadvantages associated with that.

Conclusion

Crisis management is playing a crucial role in modern business conducting because crises are an issue in today’s economy. “In the course of time, with the development of society and technical and technological innovations of various kinds, the frequency of crisis phenomena has increased”(Brezina, et al., 2024). Therefore crisis management should be reviewed precisely. The first body paragraph reviews crises as phenomena, a process of crisis management, and its significance for modern businesses. The second body paragraph describes the main functions, including prevention, planning, response, and recovery, relying on other research works. While the third body paragraph gives information on the topic of types of crisis management, revealing two main types of managing crises- active and passive. And finally, fourth body paragraph gives some predictions for the development of crisis management in the future, especially about innovative technology use. So, this research work is focused on the term “crisis management”, functions of that phenomenon, including prevention, planning, response, and recovery, and future technological progress of crisis management.

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